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**FRIENDLINESS OF THE HOME ENVIRONMENT AS A FACTOR OF
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF THE INDIVIDUAL
ДРУЖНІСТЬ ДОМАШНЬОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА ЯК ЧИННИК
ПСИХОЛОГІЧНОГО БЛАГОПОЛУЧЧЯ ОСОБИСТОСТІ**

Аргументується висока актуальність вивчення та оцінки життєвих середовищ проживання людини, зокрема, домашнього середовища. Зазначається, що домашнє середовище являє собою важливий еко-соціальний ресурс підтримання психологічного благополуччя людини. Вводиться поняття оружності домашнього середовища.

Ключові слова: *дружність домашнього середовища, дім, домашнє середовище, психологічне благополуччя.*

It is difficult to overestimate the role of the home environment in the process of acquiring personal and social identity. Home and dwelling fulfill many important functions in human life. It is a place where one can do something useful or interesting, a protection from the elements and ill-wishers, it is a soil, a foundation, a «rear». From here a person enters other social spaces and strives to return here. Home is a metaphor of personality, the result of the subject's life creation and, at the same time, the source of its change. A person builds a house, and a person is judged by the house. Using the terminology of coping behavior, we can say that the home environment is an essential ecosocial resource for maintaining psychological well-being, overcoming difficult life situations and getting out of stresses (Savage, 2003). It is a special naturally formed socio-physical space in which attachments are established and biographical events take place, a significant component of the empirical personality. All this, it would seem, should make the home space the object of close attention of specialists from different fields of knowledge: anthropologists, social and ecological psychologists, and personologists. However, this is not the case: in Russia, due to the well-known social circumstances that made the housing problem extremely painful for many Russians, identification with the house did not occur, and not every communal house dweller would agree that a small room is a symbol of his personality. In the pursuit of asceticism and functionality, Russian architecture has long forgotten the «bourgeois» concept of coziness (Высоковский, 2002, Чеснокова, 2013). And abroad the study of home space is also not very popular, because if a house does not suit its owner, it can be changed to a more preferable dwelling without a long and sometimes difficult reconstruction of home space. Most studies of home psychology are supported by real estate companies, where it is well understood that finding a suitable home for a person is a difficult problem, and it is difficult to solve it without psychologists (Coolen, 2008; 2011).

The studies initiated by the authorities of some countries to reconstruct urban living spaces (Renewal programs) in order to achieve compactness and environmental friendliness of the settlement are also related to this problematic.

There are other arguments in favor of studying home space. Surprisingly, when studying adolescent deviations, such as tendency to vagrancy, running away from home, neither social nor clinical psychologists ask about the quality of the home environment from which the adolescent runs away, and the reasons for his/her lack of attachment to home [32]. Meanwhile, American and Swedish psychologists have shown that adolescents who are homebound and intend to stay with their parents after graduation are more psychologically well off than those who plan to leave (Morgan, 2010; Nordström, 2014). The next complex social problem is the adaptation of orphans who are unable to live in their own apartment, which they receive after leaving the orphanage, resulting in the risk of homelessness.

Interaction with the home space should also be studied to predict the behavior and well-being of people living in substitute territories: in special boarding schools for gifted children or in cadet colleges, where children study away from their own families, as well as in shelters for the elderly and palliative care hospitals. The so-called therapeutic environment that facilitates adaptation and orientation of different vulnerable groups, in particular, elderly people with signs of senile dementia (there is even an expression «dementia-friendly environment») is studied abroad (Ritchie, Edgerton, 2014). Friendliness of the environment is a key therapeutic factor for migrants and repatriates, whether forced or voluntary. Since in the situation of separation from the habitual place of residence the feeling of longing and attachment to the native place increases, the new environment should be organized taking into account the national, social and other characteristics of migrants. Only then will a person be able to adapt to the new place faster.

An examination of the friendliness of the home space is also necessary in cases of conflictual divorces or in the adoption decision-making process. Finally, many family conflicts related to changes in family composition are also conditioned by the quality of family members' attitudes and the measure of control over the home space. Thus, it is clear that in different research and applied contexts, there is a need to study, assess and measure the quality of a person's home environment.

In foreign environmental psychology there are several terms to designate home space – for example, they speak about the house as a physical object (house), possessing architectural and interior characteristics; it is described as a stable, emotionally significant place, providing continuity of personal and family history (home), and also simply refers to a dwelling – in this case the house is evaluated mainly functionally, for example, as large, comfortable, well located. The presence of these semiotic nuances certifies the fact that the home environment can be perceived in the context of various human needs (vital,

social, existential), which are usually closely intertwined and tend to be satisfied in the home environment (Резниченко, 2013).

When describing human living environments in ecological psychology, either objective properties of this environment (functionality, wear and tear) or subjective ones (the degree to which it is attractive, safe and pleasant for the subject) are noted (Нартова-Бочавер, 2006). In other words, there is no universal environment suitable for everyone, which explains the failures of environmental and architectural modeling, which was carried out without reference to the opinion of non-professional consumers who assume to live in this environment. The home environment exists not as a molecular, but as a molar phenomenon: it combines functional and emotional, intertwining, mutually reinforcing and reflecting in the behavior of the inhabitants of the house (Бочавер, 2014). Therefore, in order to obtain the necessary information about its quality, on the one hand, it is necessary to possess objective information about what it is suitable for, on the other hand, one should not forget to ask the subject living or intending to live in it how much he likes it and why. «The phenomenon of coziness manifests itself not so much in filling the dwelling with material traces and signs as in people's feelings and meanings... The whole process of settling in can be imagined as a gradual transformation of the surroundings into the environment, an increasingly complete assimilation of things, people, as well as memories and images into it... The state in which the living environment exists simultaneously with a positive reflection verified in relation to it can be called a state of coziness,» writes architect A. A. Vysokovsky. (cited in Чеснокова, 2013).

As the main characteristic of the living (including home) environment of a person, we propose to consider its friendliness in relation to the inhabitant, which we understand as a measure of compliance of the existing and perceived capabilities of the environment to the needs of the subject in it. According to the level of friendliness expression we can distinguish the following four types of living environments: threatening environment prevents the satisfaction of basic human needs and mobilizes protective activity; safe environment allows a person to lead a balanced, adapted way of life, but does not provide resources for development; friendly environment provides opportunities for favorable development and self-actualization; finally, psychotherapeutic environment is capable of having a compensatory, healing and stimulating influence on the development of the whole system. The ideal combines the characteristics of a friendly and a psychotherapeutic environment: it is an environment enriched with sensory information, legible, responsive and docile – often reminiscent of something familiar and personalized (Ritchie, Edgerton, 2014).

The mechanisms of human interaction with the environment – signification and personalization – have been analyzed by us in previously published works (Нартова-Бочавер, 2003). In this interaction we can conditionally distinguish objective and subjective levels. The objective level is set by the affordances of the environment, i.e. the opportunities it provides to the

acting subject (Greeno, 1994; Heft, 2001; Kytä, 2004). The greater the number of such opportunities, the richer and more differentiated the environment is. However, some assumptions remain formal and cannot be used due to social rules: in fact, compositions of assumptions form areas of free spontaneous, supported and forbidden activity (Costall, 1995).

The subjective level of interaction is set by a person's sense of place and the measure of attachment to his or her home, which are associated with positive experiences, memories, the role of the home in the family history and personal biography (Резниченко, 2013).

Obviously, the assessment of the friendliness of the environment requires the use of two instruments: one of them should be set by the objective characteristics of the house, the other – by the subject's experiences related to the dwelling. If we assume that the assessment of the environment will have a scale character (and it is the standard tool that is the most economical and reliable), then the units of its units of its increment and measurement can be separate objective functions of the dwelling that satisfy the needs of its inhabitants. At the same time, although the subject may be irrationally attached to the objectively non-resource home, it seems reasonable to begin the study of the home environment with the assessment of its functionality. The subject of our attention is the house as a dwelling.